

1 **Feed restriction in mid-lactation dairy cows. I: Effects on milk production**
 2 **and energy-related blood metabolites.**

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6 **Supplemental materials and methods**

7 **Supplemental tables**

8 **Supplementary Table S1.** Concentrations of blood metabolites associated with
 9 acute-phase response and liver function during the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted (FR)
 10 diets.

<i>Item</i>	<i>Diet</i>			<i>P-values</i>		
	AL	FR	SEM	Diet ¹	Day	Trt x Day ²
<i>Acute-Phase Response</i>						
Total protein, g/dL	7.83	7.70	0.12	0.40	<0.01	0.44
Albumin, g/dL	3.29	3.12	0.05	0.01	0.49	0.05
Globulin, g/dL	4.57	4.50	0.09	0.54	<0.01	0.45
Haptoglobin, mg/ml	0.80	0.74	0.16	0.48	0.23	0.12
Serum amyloid A, ng/ml	44.8	74.1	39.0	0.91	0.44	0.83
<i>Liver Function³</i>						
APT, U/L	39.4	36.7	1.8	0.21	0.01	0.60
AST, U/L	71.5	73.1	4.5	0.78	<0.01	0.27
GGT, U/L	28.5	28.5	0.7	0.98	<0.01	0.04
GDH, U/L	50.8	58.9	22.8	0.40	<0.01	0.92
Bilirubin, mg/dL	0.17	0.26	0.04	0.02	<0.01	0.16

11 ¹*P*-value of the orthogonal contrast between the ad libitum (AL) and feed restricted
 12 (FR) diets.

13 ²*P*-value of the interactions Treatment by Day belong to the comparison between
 14 the seven treatments.

15 ³ APT = Alkaline phosphatase; AST = Aspartate aminotransferase; GGT =
 16 γ - glutamyl transferase; GDH = Glutamate dehydrogenase.

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Supplementary Table S2. Concentrations of blood metabolites associated with acute-phase response and liver function during the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted (FR) diets per day.

Item	Diet	Day					SEM	P-values		
		1	2	3	4	5		Diet x Day ²	Trend ¹	
<i>Acute-Phase Response</i>										
Total protein, g/dL	AL	7.78	7.98	7.73	7.63	7.93	0.18	0.43	0.94	0.58
	FR	7.68	7.6	7.65	7.48	7.7	0.14	0.53	0.86	0.43
Albumin, g/dL	AL	3.33	3.33	3.18	3.28	3.33	0.1	0.77	0.83	0.27
	FR	3.22	3.12	3.05	3.05	3.15	0.06	0.25	0.32	0.03
Globulin, g/dL	AL	4.43	4.73	4.53	4.43	4.68	0.17	0.13	0.61	1
	FR	4.4	4.6	4.58	4.4	4.53	0.09	0.18	0.86	0.32
Haptoglobin, mg/ml	AL	0.64	0.69 ^a	0.67 ^a	0.77 ^a	1.20	0.23	0.03	0.11	0.2
	FR	0.84	0.86	0.74	0.7	0.58	0.18	0.53	0.24	0.74
Serum amyloid A, ng/ml	AL	27.1	43.3	45.2	47.4	61	58.5	0.96	0.7	0.98
	FR	78.1	83.8	72.3	66.1	70.1	46.4	0.88	0.82	0.99
<i>Liver Function³</i>										
APT, U/L	AL	39.4	39.7	38.7	38.7	40.2	2.3	0.94	0.93	0.61
	FR	37.8	39.1	37.1	35.1	34.6	1.9	0.16	0.07	0.48
AAT, U/L	AL	74.6	74.2	70.2	69.7	69.2	6.1	0.91	0.48	0.85
	FR	74.3	75.8	76.5	71	67.8	4.7	0.47	0.27	0.26
GGT, U/L	AL	29.1	30.1 ^a	28.6 ^a	26.1 ^b	28.6	1.1	0.06	0.8	0.8
	FR	28.2	28.6	28.9	27.5	29.1	1.1	0.42	0.19	0.61
GDH, U/L	AL	58.4	58.1	55.4	56	51.8	24.6	0.93	0.85	0.94
	FR	87.7	83.5	74.8	56.6	37.8	18.8	0.41	0.04	0.42
Bilirubin, mg/dL	AL	0.2	0.18	0.13	0.18	0.18	0.06	0.32	0.88	0.5
	FR	0.17	0.26 ^a	0.31 ^a	0.26 ^a	0.29	0.05	0.03	0.15	0.12

^{a,b,c}Means in a row with superscripts without a common letter differ, $P \leq 0.05$.

¹ P-values of the test for linear or quadratic trends.

² P-value of the interaction of each diet (AL and FR) with day. Extracted from the SLICE statement output within the interaction of treatment with day.

³ APT = Alkaline phosphatase; AST = Aspartate aminotransferase; GGT = γ - glutamyl transferase; GDH = Glutamate dehydrogenase.

Supplementary Table S3. Concentrations ($\mu\text{mol/dL}$) of blood metabolites related with N metabolism of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted (FR) diets per day.

Item ¹	Diet			<i>P</i> – values ²				
	AL	FR	SEM	Diet ³	Day	Trt x Day	Hour	Trt x Hour
Carnosine	1.29	1.09	0.19	0.37	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.99
Cystathionine	0.14	0.15	0.03	0.68	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.88
Ethanolamine	0.40	0.37	0.04	0.12	0.02	0.03	0.29	0.97
Hydroxyproline	1.03	1.13	0.20	0.37	0.09	0.89	<0.01	0.5
PEA	2.02	2.15	0.15	0.51	0.02	<0.01	0.05	0.97
Phosphoserine	1.42	1.33	0.09	0.48	<0.01	<0.01	0.06	0.99
Sarcosine	0.56	0.51	0.14	0.8	<0.01	<0.01	0.2	0.45
Taurine	6.03	5.76	1.04	0.55	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.85
α -AAA	0.70	0.92	0.10	0.11	<0.01	0.27	0.53	<0.01
α -ABA	1.65	1.87	0.20	0.43	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.99
β -Alanine	0.22	0.24	0.06	0.55	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	0.91

¹PEA = Phosphoethanolamine; α -AAA = α -amino adipic acid; α -ABA = α -amino butyric acid.

²*P*-value of the interactions (Treatment by Day and by Hour) belong to the comparison between the seven treatments.

³*P*-value of the orthogonal contrast between the ad libitum (AL) and feed restricted (FR) diets.

Supplementary Table S4. Concentrations of blood metabolites related with nitrogen metabolism of mid-lactation dairy cows during 5 days on the ad libitum (AL) and feed-restricted (FR) diets per day.

Item ¹	Diet	Day					SEM	P-values		
		1	2	3	4	5		Diet x Day ²	Trend ³	
									Lin.	Quad.
Carnosine	AL	1.2	1.28	1.27	1.33	1.36	0.21	0.49	0.13	0.99
	FR	1.17	1.12	1.05	1.06	1.05	0.14	0.39	0.1	0.31
Cystathionine	AL	0.14 ^{bc}	0.14 ^b	0.16 ^a	0.16 ^{ab}	0.13 ^c	0.03	<0.01	0.86	0.05
	FR	0.15 ^a	0.15 ^{ab}	0.15 ^{ab}	0.15 ^{ab}	0.14 ^b	0.02	0.24	0.31	0.93
Ethanolamine	AL	0.38	0.38	0.41	0.42	0.41	0.04	0.73	0.27	0.64
	FR	0.37 ^{ab}	0.36 ^b	0.41 ^a	0.36 ^b	0.36 ^b	0.04	<0.01	0.62	0.22
Hydroxyproline	AL	1.09	0.96	1.05	1.07	1.01	0.19	0.68	0.92	0.92
	FR	1.11 ^{ab}	1.22 ^a	1.15 ^{ab}	1.23 ^a	1.08 ^b	0.15	0.13	0.88	0.28
PEA	AL	2.08	1.97	2.03	1.99	2.01	0.17	0.85	0.71	0.63
	FR	2.09 ^b	2.05 ^b	2.17 ^{ab}	2.13 ^b	2.29 ^a	0.13	0.08	0.04	0.31
Phosphoserine	AL	1.55 ^d	1.47 ^{cd}	1.42 ^{bc}	1.35 ^{ab}	1.30 ^a	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	0.83
	FR	1.36	1.35	1.32	1.31	1.31	0.07	0.84	0.18	0.67
Sarcosine	AL	0.55	0.56	0.58	0.58	0.53	0.15	0.6	0.89	0.39
	FR	0.45 ^b	0.48 ^b	0.52 ^{ab}	0.54 ^a	0.57 ^a	0.1	<0.01	0.01	0.88
Taurine	AL	6.07	6.1	5.89	6.2	5.91	1.15	0.92	0.91	0.96
	FR	5.92	5.73	5.58	5.6	5.99	0.81	0.96	1	0.38
α- AAA	AL	0.67	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.7	0.12	0.97	0.86	0.53
	FR	0.78 ^{bc}	0.72 ^c	0.79 ^c	0.97 ^{ab}	1.02 ^a	0.11	0.03	0.01	0.1
α-ABA	AL	1.47	1.65	1.77	1.79	1.65	0.26	0.16	0.4	0.02
	FR	1.50 ^d	1.71 ^c	1.93 ^b	2.10 ^a	2.14 ^{ab}	0.18	<0.01	<0.01	0.1
β-Alanine	AL	0.23	0.21	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.06	0.85	0.78	0.92
	FR	0.25	0.23	0.22	0.26	0.26	0.05	0.39	0.42	0.14

¹ PEA = Phosphoethanolamine; α-AAA = α-amino adipic acid; α-ABA = α-amino butyric acid.

²P-value of the interaction of each diet (AL and FR) with day. Extracted from the SLICE statement output within the interaction of treatment with day.

³P-values of the test for linear or quadratic trends.

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